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PROCEEDINGS BOOK

ABSTRACTS

Plenary Lectures
Invited Lectures
Oral Presentations
Posters

Since detection/quantification of low levels of disease in plasma is still challenging regarding analytical and clinical validations, we assessed association of baseline ctDNA presence/level with the clinical course of melanoma.

Patients and Methods: The study included 61 patients with BRAF-positive melanoma in clinical stage III/IV. All patients received ICI as adjuvant/neoadjuvant therapy. Cell-free DNA (cfDNA) was extracted from plasma samples using the MagCore Plasma DNA Extraction Kit (1.2 mL). CtDNA was quantified via BRAF V600 mutation using the QIAcuity Digital PCR System.

Results: Patients with detectable ctDNA more frequently experienced disease progression ($p=0.06$). The average fraction of variant allele (VAF) was significantly higher in patients who experienced disease progression (0.15 vs. 0.06; $p=0.02$). When VAF of 0.15 was used as cut off (also obtained by ROC analysis), superior duration of progression free survival and overall survival were observed in patients with VAF < 0.15 (median PFS 13.91 vs. 1.64 months, $p=0.02$; median OS 18.91 vs. 7.63 months, $p=0.041$).

Conclusions: The ctDNA presence/fraction at baseline may be considered as a marker of poor prognosis. In order to confirm these findings, a larger cohort of patients is needed to allow broader statistical analyses.

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P44

The use of pleural effusion from patients with lung cancer as a source of extracellular vesicles – first report from the EXPAND-EV project

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Keywords: Carcinoma, Non-Small-Cell Lung, Extracellular Vesicles, Pleural Effusion

Background: Pleural effusion (PE) is a frequent complication of lung cancer (LC), occurring in up to one-quarter of patients. Despite being routinely sampled for diagnostic cytology, its sensitivity is often insufficient, leaving a need for complementary molecular approaches. Small extracellular vesicles (sEVs) from PE are enriched in tumor-related proteins and RNAs and could serve as a form of liquid biopsy. Most studies have relied on ultracentrifugation (UC), but this method yields low-purity isolates, often unsuitable for proteomic profiling. Improved results were obtained by combining UC with size-exclusion chromatography (UC-SEC), while ExoProK introduced Proteinase K pretreatment to reduce contaminants. Nevertheless, clinically feasible and standardized protocols for PE-derived EVs are still missing. Within the EXPAND-EV EU project, we focused on EV isolation from PE of patients with advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), evaluating methods which emphasize minimal input volume, short turnaround time, and compatibility with downstream omics.

Materials and Methods: sEVs from PE samples were isolated by three approaches: (1) an in-house spherical porous methacrylate-based polymer functionalized with VHH antibodies (chromatography-based method, CH), (2) UC, and (3) a commercial Norgen kit (CK). Vesicles were characterized using nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and flow cytometry for CD9 expression. Methods were compared for efficiency, purity, and clinical applicability.

Results: Both CH and CK enabled isolation from as little as 1 mL, while UC required ≥ 12 mL. CK was the fastest, followed by CH, whereas UC was time-consuming. CH yielded the highest particle counts and cleanest profiles, with UC producing the lowest yield and greatest protein contamination. TEM, AFM, and flow cytometry confirmed vesicular morphology and integrity, with CH isolates showing the highest purity.

Conclusions: CH and CK approaches are practical alternatives to UC, enabling efficient EV isolation from small PE volumes. CH isolates are suitable for proteomics, while CK combines speed with RNA recovery, supporting transcriptomic

analysis. LC-MS/MS profiling of PE-derived vesicles using the Norgen kit with additional pretreatment with Proteinase K (as in ExoProK) or a CK-SEC combination to enhance purity may help establish PE-derived EVs as a valuable source for biomarker discovery in LC.

Acknowledgments and funding: This study was funded by the Horizon Europe EXPAND_EV (HORIZON-MSCA-2023-SE-01, Grant Agreement No. 101182851) and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Agreement No. 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200043).

P45

Liquid Biopsy as a Tool in Guiding Anti-EGFR Monoclonal Antibody Rechallenge Therapy in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer

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Keywords: metastatic colorectal cancer (mCRC), liquid biopsy (LB), anti-EGFR antibodies, rechallenge therapy

Background: In patients with metastatic colorectal cancer (mCRC) who progressed to anti-EGFR monoclonal antibody (mAb) therapy, such as cetuximab and panitumumab, a rechallenge with the same agents is becoming a promising approach. Although patients demonstrate objective progression during the anti-EGFR treatment, emerging findings suggest that anti-EGFR-resistant clones decay, enabling the possibility of a rechallenge strategy (1). A key step for a deeper understanding of clinical progression in patients is the identification of mechanisms of secondary resistance to anti-EGFR mAb therapies. Limited data are currently available on the resistance mechanism that develops during the anti-EGFR treatment. Intratumoral heterogeneity is assumed to play a significant role in mCRC progression. During anti-EGFR therapy, subclones continuously arise through genomic mutations, resulting in faster disease progression and poorer overall survival (OS) in patients (2). Santini et al. (3) demonstrated that the reuse of cetuximab was a potentially effective strategy in patients with mCRC who had previously achieved clinical benefit from cetuximab-based therapy. A sufficiently lengthy treatment-free period, of a minimum of four and optimally longer than six months, should be provided. This study was the first to lay the groundwork for the hypothesis that acquired resistance to anti-EGFR therapy may be reversible and that, after a break from the therapy, the tumor may become sensitive again, which improves subsequent response and increases patient free survival (PFS). European and American health authorities have restricted the use of cetuximab and panitumumab, as mono- or in combination with chemotherapy, only to patients with wild-type (wt) RAS gene status (4). As with first-line treatment, confirmation of wt KRAS/NRAS gene status is recommended for anti-EGFR mAb reintroduction (5). Mutations in the BRAF gene are also recognized as negative prognostic markers in the response to the anti-EGFR therapy, and according to the European Society For Medical Oncology (ESMO) guidelines, testing for mutations in the BRAF gene is also recommended (6). The preferred method for selecting patients for the rechallenge strategy, but also for detecting mutations and monitoring secondary resistance, is liquid biopsy (LB). LB is a minimally invasive technique that shows promise in identifying various molecular changes crucial for achieving an effective response to treatment.

In our research, we aimed to analyze the distribution of mutations and characteristics of circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) in plasma samples from patients who developed resistance to the anti-EGFR antibodies. This study may enhance our understanding of the mechanisms underlying the evolution of resistance to targeted therapies.

Materials and methods: Samples were collected from 25 patients (17 male/8 female), potential candidates for rechallenge therapy, over a period of 7 months. The median age of the study population was 64 years (range: 40-80 years). Among the 25 patients enrolled, 15 received cetuximab and 10 received panitumumab, before disease progression. Patients were included if the previous anti-EGFR therapy had been applied for at least 6 months. According to Santini's hypothesis (3), blood was sampled at least 4 months after receiving the last mAb-based therapy. The blood